

Copper-Catalyzed Cyclization of Oxime Acetates with DMSO as C1 Synthons for Construction of Pyridines: A New Alternative Approach to Symmetrical Pyridines

Authors

Boniface Opio, Siddaiah Vidavalur, Kamala Pamula, Elizabeth Smith Yalla, Vineetha Kodumuru, Chandana Gottumukkala, Zenebe Hagos Wube

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530003, Andhra Pradesh-India

Corresponding author : Boniface Opio

Abstract

A facile copper-catalyzed cyclization of oxime acetates with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) for the construction of symmetrical pyridines has been developed *via* N-O bond cleavage. A methyl carbon on DMSO is used as a source of one carbon synthon in the presence of NaHSO₃ as the base. The reaction proceeds smoothly with a broad range of substrates, giving access to a variety of symmetrical pyridine derivatives in moderate to good yields. This methodology features use of low-cost catalysts, and avoids usage of ligands and additives.

Graphical abstract

Keywords: Cyclization, DMSO, Oxime acetates, Symmetrical pyridines, Copper-Catalysis, N-O cleavage

Introduction

Pyridines constitute a significant category of heterocycles that are widely found in natural products, functional materials, and the realm of medicinal chemistry.^[1] In particular, certain symmetrical pyridines have been found to exhibit strong biological activity.^[2] Important biological characteristics of pyridines include antioxidant, anticancer, anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory, anti-HIV, anti-malarial, anticonvulsant, vasodilator and antiepileptic activities.^[3a-d] Additionally, several compounds with pyridine core units are employed as medicinal substances (**Fig. 1**).^[4]

Fig.1: Some of the bioactive compounds containing pyridine core units.

In the context of synthetic chemistry, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is primarily utilized as a high-boiling point polar aprotic solvent with a secondary role as a mild and inexpensive oxidant.^[5] DMSO for long was not thought of as a substrate, building block, or synthon in organic transformations. However, an abundance of reports has recently appeared to demonstrate that dimethyl sulfoxide is capable of serving in these roles.^[6]

DMSO is made up of two methyl groups (CH_3) and a sulfur atom bound to an oxygen atom which gives it a trigonal pyramidal structure. This structure makes it an excellent solvent due to its broad range of chemical dissolving properties with specific reactivity patterns that can be leveraged in chemical reactions.^[7] However, DMSO can also function as a carbon source in some chemical reaction; especially, for reactions where DMSO itself aids in conversions or where the sulfur (S) in DMSO aids in the production of organic fragments that can contribute carbon atoms to the process. As an essential precursor, DMSO effectively adds a range of functional fragments to organic compounds, such as substituents like; $-\text{Me}$, $-\text{CH}$, $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{SMe}_2$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{SMe}$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{SOMe}$, $-\text{SMe}$, $-\text{SO}_2\text{Me}$, $-\text{SOMe}$, or O.^[8]

Conversely, oxime acetates, find application in heterocyclic synthesis owing to their capacity to engage in diverse electrophilic cyclization reactions, produce reactive intermediates, and offer both regioselective and stereoselective control.^[9] Their adaptability renders them indispensable in the synthesis of intricate heterocycles containing nitrogen or oxygen, which play a crucial role in numerous domains of chemistry and pharmaceutical advancement.^[10]

Many techniques for the synthesis of pyridines have been developed during the past few decades, including condensation of amines and carbonyl compounds,^[11] transition metal-catalyzed cycloaddition events,^[12] and cycloisomerization reactions.^[13] These techniques, however, are primarily concerned with adaptable unsymmetrical substituted pyridines.^[14] In contrast, there has been few reports of a comprehensive process for the synthesis of useful symmetrical pyridines.^[15] Hence, there remains ample scope to design new strategies for pyridine synthesis employing inexpensive catalysts, readily available partners, and environmentally benign reactions. The N-O

bond cleavage of the ketoxime acetates acts as an internal oxidant to enable the reactions to proceed under mild redox-neutral conditions.^[16] Recently, transition-metal-catalyzed coupling of ketoxime acetates with aldehydes for the synthesis of symmetrical pyridines has emerged as a simple method to synthesize substituted pyridines (**Scheme 1a**).^[17] Mi-Na Zhao and group also reported a novel ruthenium-catalyzed cyclization of ketoxime acetates with DMF for the synthesis of symmetrical pyridines (**Scheme 1b**).^[18] Encouraged by some of these works, our team disclosed a FeCl₃-catalyzed cyclization of ketoxime acetates and CClF₂COONa for the assembly of symmetrical pyridines (**Scheme 1c**).^[19] Despite these elegant protocols, there remains some drawbacks, such as the usage of expensive transition metal catalysts, oxidants, unfriendly additives, low yields, and harsh reaction conditions. Therefore, in continuation of our research work on the development of new synthetic methodologies for heterocyclic compounds, herein, we describe a simple and efficient protocol for the synthesis of symmetrically substituted pyridines from oxime acetates and DMSO in the presence of copper (I) chloride as catalyst, and NaHSO₃ as base at 120 °C for 6 h under nitrogen atmosphere (**Scheme 1d**).

Previous works:

Our previous work:

This work:

Scheme 1: Synthesis of symmetrical pyridines

Results And Discussion

To Investigate the feasibility of this protocol, the author initiated the scrutiny by taking oxime acetate (**1a**) and DMSO (**2**) as model substrates in the presence of CuCl (10 mol%), catalyst at 100 °C under nitrogen atmosphere (**Table 1**). To our gratification, the desired product 2,6-diphenyl substituted pyridine(**3a**) was obtained in 60% yield after 6 h of reaction (**Table 1, entry 1**). However, the yield of **3a** dropped noticeably to 23 % when the reaction was performed under air (**Table 1, entry 2**), presumably due to hydrolysis of the oxime acetate. To our amazement, the yield of **3a** was impressively increased to 92 %, when we raised the bath temperature to 120 °C (**Table 1, entry 3**), whereas a further increase to 140 °C resulted into a slight decline (78%, **Table 1, entry 4**), establishing 120 °C as the optimal temperature. To enhance on the yield and subsequently rate of formation of **3a**, we carefully examined the influence of the other reaction parameters like catalysts and bases at 120 °C under nitrogen atmosphere.

A number of different copper salts such as CuI, CuCl₂, CuBr, and Cu (OAc)₂ was screened at 120 °C in DMSO (**Table 1, entries 5-7**). Among all the catalysts examined, CuCl (20 mol %) showed the best activity with a yield of 92 % (**Table 1, entry 3**). It was also observed that no desired product could be formed in the absence of copper catalysts (**Table 1, entry 8**). Further investigation of the base effect revealed that, NaHSO₃ was superior to the other bases including Na₂CO₃, K₂CO₃, Cs₂CO₃, Et₃N (**Table 1, entries 9-13**). This investigation also indicated that the base was very essential for this reaction since no target product was formed in the absence of the base (**Table 1, entry 14**). Variation in catalyst loading showed no significant improvement because increasing the catalyst concentration to 30 mol% led to a lower yield to 80%, while reducing it to 10 mol% also decreased the yield (**Table 1, compare entries 3, 15, and 16**). These results collectively identify **CuCl (20 mol%)** and **NaHSO₃ (0.5 equiv.)** at 120 °C under nitrogen as the optimal conditions for the formation of **3a**.

With the optimized conditions established, we next examined the substrate scope of the reaction using a variety of ketoxime acetates (**1**) and dimethyl sulfoxide (**2**). As shown in **Scheme 2**, the model reaction between unsubstituted acetophenone oxime acetate (**1a**) and dimethyl sulfoxide (**2**) afforded the desired product 2,6-diphenyl pyridine (**3a**) in 92% yield. Encouraged by this result, a broad range of oxime acetates was explored to evaluate the generality of the method. Furthermore, we explored the reaction between different substituted oxime acetates and DMSO, which produced the respective products (**3a-3p**) in moderate to good yields. As shown in **Scheme 2**, oxime acetates bearing a variety of functional groups (electron donating groups) such as 4-Me, 4-OMe and 3,4-di-OMe on the aromatic ring reacted successfully and gave the corresponding pyridines in excellent yields (**Scheme 2, 3b, 3c & 3i**). Meanwhile, oxime acetates containing weak electron-withdrawing groups due to presence of the halogen atoms (4-F, 4-Cl, 2,4-di-Cl 4-Br, 3-Br) on the ring also took part in this transformation effectively to give the target symmetrical pyridines in good yields (**Scheme 2, 3d – 3h**). Moreover, all of the halogen atoms remained intact in this reaction, which could provide opportunities for further functionalization. Additionally, oxime acetate with a strong electron-withdrawing substituent on the aromatic ring (4-NO₂)

proceeded smoothly and provided **3j** in **72%** yields. Interestingly, ketoxime acetates derived from heterocyclic ketones like pyridine, furan and thiophene could be transformed as well in this reaction and gave the corresponding pyridines in good yields (**Scheme 2, 3k-3m**) in 73%, 75% and 64% yields, respectively.

Furthermore, this protocol was also compatible with oxime acetates derived from α -tetralone and α -indanone which generated the desired condensed-substituted pyridines (**Scheme 2, 3n and 3o**) in 67% and 61% yields, respectively. Besides acetophenone oxime acetates, oxime acetates derived from propiophenone underwent chemical transformation to give product **3p** in 68% yield. However, to our dismay, the reaction of oxime acetates obtained from aliphatic ketones like ethyl methyl ketone and cyclic ketones, example cyclohexanone didn't yield any fruit as far as the expected product **3a** was concerned. This could be caused by the presence of less stable iminyl radical in each, which makes them less reactive.^[24-26] The low reactivity for the case of ethyl methyl ketone could also result from the two relatively large alkyl groups surrounding the carbonyl carbon. This generates steric hindrance, making it impossible for the nucleophiles to approach and attack the carbonyl group.^[27, 28]

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions.^a

Entry	Catalyst (mol %)	Base	Temperature (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
1	CuCl (10)	NaHSO ₃	100	60
2	CuCl (20)	NaHSO ₃	100	23 ^c
3	CuCl (20)	NaHSO₃	120	92
4	CuCl (20)	NaHSO ₃	140	78
5	CuI (20)	NaHSO ₃	120	76
6	CuBr (20)	NaHSO ₃	120	74
7	Cu(OAc) ₂ (20)	NaHSO ₃	120	71
8	-	NaHSO ₃	120	NR
9	CuCl (20)	NaHCO ₃	120	78
10	CuCl (20)	Na ₂ CO ₃	120	65
11	CuCl (20)	K ₂ CO ₃	120	57
12	CuCl (20)	Cs ₂ CO ₃	120	52
13	CuCl (20)	Et ₃ N	120	41
14	CuCl (20)	-	120	NR
15	CuCl (30)	NaHSO ₃	120	80
16	CuCl (10)	NaHSO ₃	120	68

“Optimized reaction conditions: **1** (0.1 mmol), **2** (2mL), catalyst (20 mol %), base (0.5 equiv.), temp 120 °C, 6 h under nitrogen atmosphere. ^bIsolated yields, ^cunder air atmosphere, **NR** = No reaction.

“Reaction conditions: **1** (0.1 mmol), **2** (2mL), CuCl (20 mol%), NaHSO₃ (0.5 equiv.), 120 °C, 12 h under nitrogen atmosphere.

Scheme 2: Substrate scope of various oxime acetates

To enlighten on the mechanism of this transformation, we performed a sequence of control experiments as summarized in **Scheme 3**. An investigation of the reaction between acetophenone oxime acetate (**1a**) and dimethyl sulfoxide under optimized conditions was conducted by the addition of chain breaking antioxidants (radical scavengers) like TEMPO ((2,2,6,6-tetramethyl piperidin-1-yl) oxyl), (**Scheme 3 (i)**) or BHT (butylated hydroxytoluene) (**Scheme 3 (ii)**) to the reaction mixture. In both cases, the formation of the desired product was completely suppressed, indicating that the reaction likely proceeds through a radical pathway.

Scheme 3: Control experiments.

Scheme 4: Plausible Mechanism

On the basis of control experiments and previous reports ^[20,21,22] on copper-catalyzed transformations of oxime derivatives, a plausible reaction mechanism is proposed in **Scheme 4**. Initially, oxime acetate **1a** reacts with CuCl to generate an iminylcopper (II) species (**A**) through a sequential single-electron reduction of the N–O bond. Subsequent tautomerization of **A** affords a copper (II) enamide intermediate (**B**), which then acts as a nucleophile toward the dimethyl sulfoxide. Similarly, DMSO is activated by NaHSO_3 to give **C**, via the Pummerer reaction,^[23] which is then coupled by **B** generated from **1a**, producing the intermediate **D** (through nucleophilic addition of **B** to the **C**). Condensation of intermediate **D** with a second molecule of oxime acetate produces intermediate **E**, which in the presence of, NaHSO_3 , undergoes demethylthiolation and electrocyclic cyclization simultaneously to afford the α -methylenation product **F**. Finally, the desired product, 2,6-diphenylpyridine (**3a**) is formed *via* oxidative aromatization of intermediate **F** followed by the second deprotonation.

2. Experimental section:

All the chemicals used are commercially purchased from Merck, Spectrochem, and Avra and used without any further purification. For thin layer chromatography (TLC), aluminum plates coated with silica gel containing F254 indicator were used. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel (100–200 mesh) eluting with n-hexane and ethyl acetate solvents.

The ^1H NMR spectra of all synthesized compounds were recorded in Bruker 400 MHz NMR machine using their solutions in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Advance 100 MHz spectrometers, and were fully decoupled by broad band proton decoupling. The chemical shifts in both cases were recorded in parts per million (ppm) with respect to the triplet's center line at 77.16 ppm of chloroform-d. The mass data obtained from high resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded using electro spray ionization (ESI) in Bruker waters machine. The oxime acetate derivatives were synthesized according to literature procedures. [17, 18]

3. General procedure for the synthesis symmetrical pyridines (3a)

To an oven dried 25 mL round bottom flask, oxime acetate, (1), DMSO, (2), CuCl (20 mol%) and NaHSO_3 were reacted under nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was allowed to stir at 120°C for 6 h. The reaction progress was monitored by TLC hourly. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and diluted with ethyl acetate (20 mL) and water. The organic layer was separated and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Concentration using rotary evaporator under reduced pressure was carried out. The crude residue obtained was run in column chromatography for purification using silica gel as stationary phase, Hexane/EtoAc (98:2) as a mobile phase to obtain the product 3a.

Conclusion

Conclusively, we have developed a new and simple copper - catalyzed strategy for the synthesis of symmetrical pyridines from oxime acetates and DMSO. In this protocol, DMSO was used as a carbon source during cyclization reaction. Considering the good yields, accessibility of starting materials, affordability of catalyst, operational simplicity, and tolerance of a wide range of substrates, as major advantages of this protocol, we therefore, suggest that, this method would provide a good alternative pathway for the synthesis of symmetrically substituted pyridines.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) for the award of scholarship and providing funds. We also thank the Director, NMR Centre, Andhra University for timely provision of NMR spectra. The authors gratefully acknowledge all scholars, researchers, and institutions whose published works and reports informed the development of this article.

Disclosure statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. a) Abass, M. Fused Quinolines. Recent Synthetic Approaches to Azoloquinolines. *Heterocycles* **2005**, *65*, 901. DOI: 10.3987/REV-04-592. b) Gibson, V. C.; Redshaw, C.; Solan, G. A. Bis(imino)pyridines: Surprisingly Reactive Ligands and a Gateway to New Families of Catalysts. *Chem. Rev.* **2007**, *107*, 1745. DOI: 10.1021/cr068437y. c) Tomasik, P.; Ratajewicz, Z. Pyridine Metal Complexes, Part 6A. *An Interscience Publication: U. S. A.* 1985, *1*. d) Moriuchi, T.; Shen, X.; Hirao, T. Chirality Induction of π - Conjugated Chains Through Chiral Complexation. *Tetrahedron* **2006**, *62*, 12237. DOI: 10.1016/j.tet.2006.10.016. e) Bergner, B. J.; Schurmann, A.; Pepler, K.; Garsuch, A.; Janek, J. TEMPO: A Mobile Catalyst for Rechargeable Li-O₂ Batteries. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 15054. DOI: 10.1021/ja508400m. f) Wei, X.; Xu, W.; Vijayakumar, M.; Cosimbescu, L.; Liu, T.; Sprenkle, V.; Wang, W. TEMPO – Based Catholyte for High-Energy Density Nonaqueous Redox Flow Batteries. *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26*, 7649. DOI: 10.1002/adma.201403746.
2. a) Haghhighijoo, Z.; Akrami, S.; Saeedi, M.; Zonouzi, A.; Iraj, A.; Larijani, B.; Fakherzadeh, H.; Sharifi, F.; Arzaghi, S. M.; Mahdavi, M.; Edraki, N. N–Cyclohexylimidazo[1,2-a] Pyridine Derivatives as Multi-target-directed Ligands for Treatment of Alzheimer’s Disease. *Biorg. Chem.* **2020**, *103*, 104156. DOI: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2020.104146. b) Jiao, Y.; Xin, B. T.; Zhang, Y.; Wu, J.; Lu, X.; Zheng, Y.; Tang, W.; Zhou, X. Design, Synthesis and Evaluation of Novel 2-(1H-imidazol-2-yl) Pyridine Sorafenib Derivatives as Potential BRAF Inhibitors and Anti-Tumour Agent. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **2015**, *90*, 170. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2014.11.008.
3. (a) Makiura, R.; Motoyama, S.; Umemura, Y.; Yamanaka, H.; Sakata, O.; Kitagawa, H. Surface Nano-architecture of a Metal–Organic Framework. *Nat. Mater.*, 2010, *9*, 565; (b) Wang, B.; Yang, H.; Xie, Y. B., Dou, Y. B., M. J. Zhao, M.J.; Li, J.R. Controlling Structural Topology of Metal-Organic Frameworks with a Dissymmetric 4-Connected Ligand Through the Design of Metal-Containing Nodes. *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, **2016**, *27*, 502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccllet.2015.12.034> (c) Pillai, A. D.; Rathod, P. D.; Patel, P. X.; Nivsarkar, M.; Vasu, K. K.; Padh, H.; Sudarsanam, V. Novel Drug Designing Approach for Dual Inhibitors as Anti-inflammatory Agents: Implication of Pyridine Template. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, **2003**, *301*, 183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-291X\(02\)02996-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-291X(02)02996-0) (d) Candia, M. D.; Fiorella, F.; Lopopolo, G.; Carotti, A.; Romano, M. R.; Lograno, M. D.; Martel, S.; Carrupt, P.; Belviso, B. D.; Caliandro, R. Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Direct Thrombin Inhibitors Bearing 4-(piperidin-1-yl) Pyridine at the P1 Position with Potent Anticoagulant Activity. *J. Med. Chem.*, **2013**, *56*, 8696. [Doi.org/10.1021/jm401169a](https://doi.org/10.1021/jm401169a)

4. (a) Sebren, L. J.; Devery, J.; Stephenson, C. R. *ACS Catal.*, **2014**, *4*, 703; (b) Gibson, V. C.; Redshaw, C.; Solan, G. A. Bis(imino)pyridines: Surprisingly Reactive Ligands and a Gateway to New Families of Catalysts. *Chem. Rev.*, **2007**, *107*, 1745. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr068437y>. (c) Hostyn, S.; Van Baelen, G.; Lemiere, G. L. F.; Maes, B. U. W. Synthesis of α -Carbolines Starting from 2,3-Dichloropyridines and Substituted Aniline. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsc.200800077>. *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, **2008**, *350*, 2653; (d) Yadav, A. K.; Verbeeck, S.; Hostyn, S.; Franck, P.; Sergeyev, S.; Maes, B. U. "Base Effect" in the Auto-Tandem Palladium-Catalyzed Synthesis of Amino-Substituted 1-Methyl-1H- α -carbolines. *Org. Lett.*, **2013**, *15*, 1060; (e) Chelucci, G. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, **2006**, *35*, 1230. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol400064r>. (f) Wang, W.; Li, J.; Wang, K.; Smirnova, T. I.; Oldfield, E. "Pyridine Inhibitor Binding to the 4Fe-4S Protein A. aeolicus IspH (LytB): a HYSOCORE Investigation," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 6528. doi:10.1021/ja2008455
5. Zhu, X.; Zhang, F.; Kuang, D.; Deng, G.; Yang, Y.; Yu, J.; Liang, Y. K₂S as sulfur source and DMSO as carbon source for the synthesis of 2-unsubstituted benzothiazoles. *Org. Lett.* **2020**, *22*, 3793. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.0c00994>.
6. Liu, Y.F.; Ji, P.Y.; Xu, J.W.; Hu, Y.Q.; Liu, Q.; Luo, W.P.; Guo, C.C. Transition Metal-Free α -Csp³-H Methylenation of Ketones to Form C=C Bond Using Dimethyl Sulfoxide as Carbon Source. *J. chem.* **2017**, *82*, 7164. DOI: 10.1021/acs.joc.7b00619.
7. Clark, T.; Murray, J.S.; Lane, P.; Politzer, P. Why are dimethyl sulfoxide and dimethyl sulfone such good solvents? *J. Mol. Model.* **2008**, *14*, 697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00894-008-0279-y>
8. Wu, X.; Zhang, J.; Liu, S.; Gao, Q.; Wu, A. An Efficient Synthesis of Polysubstituted Pyridines via C=H Oxidation and C=S Cleavage of Dimethyl Sulfoxide. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2016**, *358*, 225. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsc.201500683>.
9. Abele, E.; Abele, R. Recent advances in the synthesis of heterocycles from oximes (2014-2017). *Curr. Org. Chem.* **2018**, *22*, 504. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2174/1385272822666180607095707>.
10. a) Maleki, B.; Solvent-free Synthesis of 2,4,6-Triarylpyridine Derivatives Promoted by 1,3-Dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin. *Org. Prep. Proced. Int.* **2015**, *47*, 173. DOI: 10.1080/00304948.2015.1005990. b) Zolfigol, M. A.; Safaiee, M.; Afsharnadery, F.; Bahrami-Nejad, N.; Baghery, S.; Salehzadeh, S.; Maleki, F. Silica Vanadic acid [SiO₂-VO(OH)₂] as an Efficient Heterogeneous Catalyst for the Synthesis of 1,2-Dihydro-1-Aryl-3H-Naphth[1,2-e] [1,3] Oxazin-3-one and 2,4,6-Triarylpyridine Derivatives via Anomeric Based Oxidation. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5*, 100546. DOI: 10.1039/C5RA21392D. c) Cave, G. W. V.; Raston, C. L.; Scott, J. L. Recent Advances in Solventless Organic Reactions Towards Benign Synthesis with Remarkable Versatility. *Chem. Commun.* **2001**, *21*, 2159. DOI: 10.1039/B106677N. d) Tu, S.; Li, T.; Shi, F.; Fang, F.; Zhu, S.; Wei, X.; Zong, Z. An Efficient Improve for the Krohnke Reaction: One-pot Synthesis of 2,4,6-Triarylpyridines Using Raw Materials under Microwave Irradiation. *Chem. Lett.*

- 2005**, *34*, 732. DOI: 10.1246/cl.2005.732. e) Zhang, X.; Wang, P.; Yuan, X.; Qin, M.; Chen, B. Synthesis of Pyridine Derivatives from Acetophenone and Ammonium Acetate by Releasing CH₄. *Asian J. Org. Chem.* **2019**, *8*, 1332. DOI: 10.1002/ajoc.201900323. f) Han, J.; Guo, X.; Liu, Y.; Fu, Y.; Yan, R.; Chen, B. One-Pot Synthesis of Benzene and Pyridine Derivatives *via* Copper-Catalyzed Coupling Reactions. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2017**, *359*, 2676. DOI: 10.1002/adsc.201700053.
11. (a) Hill, M. D. Recent Strategies for the Synthesis of Pyridine Derivatives. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2010**, *16*, 12052. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201001100> (b) Allais, C.; Liéby-Muller, F.; Constantieux, T.; Rodriguez, J. Dual Heterogeneous Catalysis for a Regioselective Three-Component Synthesis of Bi- and Tri(hetero)arylpyridines. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2012**, *354*, 2537. (c) Chen, Z.-B.; Hong, D.; Wang, Y.G. A Cascade Approach to Pyridines from 2-Azido-2,4-dienoates and α -Diazocarbonyl Compounds. *J. Org. Chem.* **2009**, *74*, 903. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo802159g>.
12. (a) Gulevich, A. V.; Dudnik, A. S.; Chernyak, N.; Gevorgyan, V. Transition Metal-Mediated Synthesis of Monocyclic Aromatic Heterocycles. *Chem. Rev.* **2013**, *113*, 3084. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr300333u>. (b) Domínguez, G.; Pérez-Castells, J. Recent advances in [2+2+2] cycloaddition reactions. *J. Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40*, 3430. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1CS15029D>.
13. (a) Nakamura, I.; Zhang, D.; Terada, M. J. Am. Copper-Catalyzed Tandem [2,3]-Rearrangement and 6π -3-Azatriene Electrocyclization in (*E*)-*O*-Propargylic α , β -Unsaturated Oximes. *Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 7884. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja102436z>. (b) Gao, H.; Zhang, J. A Dramatic Substituent Effect in Silver(I)-Catalyzed Regioselective Cyclization of *ortho*-Alkynylaryl Aldehyde Oxime Derivatives. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2009**, *351*, 85. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsc.200800568>.
14. (a) Shi, Z.; Loh, T.-P. Organocatalytic Synthesis of Highly Functionalized Pyridines at Room Temperature. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 8584. DOI 10.1002/anie.201301519. (b) Lei, C.-H.; Wang, D.-X.; Zhao, L.; Zhu, J.; Wang, M.-X. J. Am. Synthesis of Substituted Pyridines from Cascade [1 + 5] Cycloaddition of Isonitriles to *N*-Formylmethyl-Substituted Enamides, Aerobic Oxidative Aromatization, and Acyl Transfer Reaction. *Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 4708. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja401701x>. (c) Chen, M. Z.; Micalizio, G. C. J. Am. Three-Component Coupling Sequence for the Regiospecific Synthesis of Substituted Pyridines. *Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 1352. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja2105703>.
15. (a) Gholap, S. L.; Hommes, P.; Neuthe, K.; Reissig, H.-U. Per(2-thienyl) pyridines: Synthesis and Properties. *Org. Lett.* **2013**, *15*, 318. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol303231c>. (b) Rycke, N. D.; Berionni, G.; Couty, F.; Mayr, H.; Goumont, R.; David, O. R. P. Synthesis and Reactivity of Highly Nucleophilic Pyridines. *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 530. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol1029589>.

16. (a) Liu, S.; Liebeskind, L. S. A Simple, Modular Synthesis of Substituted Pyridines. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2008**, *130*, 6918. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja8013743>. (b) Parthasarathy, K.; Jeganmohan, M.; Cheng, C.-H. Rhodium-Catalyzed One-Pot Synthesis of Substituted Pyridine Derivatives from α , β -Unsaturated Ketoximes and Alkynes. *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 325. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol7028367>. (c) Too, P. C.; Wang, Y.-F.; Chiba, S. *Org. Lett.* **2010**, *12*, 5688
17. Ren, Z. H.; Zhang, Z.Y.; Yang, B. Q.; Wang, Y. Y.; Guan, Z. H. Copper-catalyzed coupling of oxime acetates with aldehydes: a new strategy for synthesis of pyridines. *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 5394
18. Mi-Na, Zhao, Rong-Rong Hui, Zhi-Hui Ren, Yao-Yu Wang, and Zheng-Hui Guan. Ruthenium-Catalyzed Cyclization of Ketoxime Acetates with DMF for Synthesis of Symmetrical Pyridines. *Org. Lett.* **2014**, *16*, 3085.
19. Varaprasad, B.; Kumar, K.B.; Siddaiah, V.; Shyamala, P.; Chinnari L. Copper-catalyzed efficient access to 2,4,6- triphenyl pyridines *via* oxidative decarboxylative coupling of aryl acetic acids with oxime acetates. *New J. Chem.*, **2021**, *45*, 15205.
20. Vodnala, N.; Singh, S.; Hazra, C.K. Lewis Acid-Promoted Typical Friedel–Crafts Reactions Using DMSO as a Carbon Source. *J. Org. Chem.* **2022**, *87*, 10053. DOI: 10.1021/acs.joc.2c01037.
21. Jiang, X.; Wang, C.; Wei, Y.; Xue, D.; Liu, Z.; Xiao, J. A General Method for N-Methylation of Amines and Nitro Compounds with Dimethylsulfoxide. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2014**, *20*, 63.
22. Wei, Y.; Yoshikai, N. Modular Pyridine Synthesis from Oximes and Enals through Synergistic Copper/Iminium Catalysis. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 3756. DOI: 10.1021/ja312346s.
23. Xiang, J.C., Gao, Q.H.; Wu, A.X. The applications of DMSO. Solvents as Reagents in Organic Synthesis: Reactions and Applications. **2017**, *20*, 353. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527805624.ch7>.
24. Qu, Z.; Tian, T.; Deng, GJ.; Huang, H. Diverse catalytic systems for nitrogen-heterocycle formation from O-acyl ketoximes. *Chinese Chem. Lett.* **2023**, *34*, 107565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccllet.2022.05.079>.
25. Guan, A. Y.; Liu, C. L.; Sun, X. F.; Xie, Y.; Wang, M. A. “Discovery of Pyridine-Based Agrochemicals by Using Intermediate Derivatization Methods,” *Bioorg. & Med. Chem.* **2016**, *24*, 342–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2015.09.031>.
26. Zhao, G.; Lin, H; Ping, Y.; Sun, H.; Zhu, S.; Xuncheng, S.; Chen, Y. Ethylenediamine-palladium (II) complexes with pyridine and its derivatives: synthesis, molecular structure and initial antitumor studies. *J. of inorg. biochem.* **1999**, *73*, 145-9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0162-0134\(99\)00009-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0162-0134(99)00009-4).

27. Jackman, MM.; Cai, Y.; Castle, SL. Recent advances in iminyl radical cyclizations. *Synthesis*. **2017**, *49*, 1785-95. DOI: 10.1055/s-0036-1588707.
28. Bowman, WR.; Bridge, CF.; Brookes, P.; Cloonan, MO.; Leach, DC. Cascade radical synthesis of heteroarenes via iminyl radicals. *J. Chem. Soc.*, **2002**, *1*, 58-68. DOI: 10.1039/B108323F.